

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant	<i>Dr. Marian Beekman</i>
Affiliation – institution	<i>Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC)</i>
Affiliation – department	<i>Biomedical Data Sciences, section of Molecular Epidemiology (MolEpi)</i>
Position	<i>Assistant Professor Molecular Epidemiology</i>
End date of contract	
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Name of the co-applicant	<i>Dr. Karin van der Pal</i>
Affiliation – institution	<i>Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC)</i>
Affiliation – department	<i>Biomedical Data Sciences, section of Advanced Data Management (ADM)</i>
Position	<i>Section head Advanced Data Management Head Research Data Competence Center</i>
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Name of the co-applicant	<i>Dr. Anna Niehues</i>
Affiliation – institution	<i>Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC)</i>
Affiliation – department	<i>Biomedical Data Sciences, section of Advanced Data Management (ADM)</i>
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Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	<i>Retrospective FAIRification by complementation of metadata and interoperability (RetroFAIR)</i>
Project duration (in months)	<i>24 months</i>

English public summary

Longitudinal observational and intervention studies with rich data from various sources are invaluable for biomedical research. Datasets such as questionnaires, physical and molecular measurements and scans often have been collected over a long period of time without FAIR principles in mind. Retrospective FAIRification is therefore essential for future reuse. While FAIR principles can guide this process, the practical implementation can be challenging. In this project, we will develop step-by-step tutorials, tools and access procedures to help biomedical researchers retrospectively FAIRify these rich datasets. This will facilitate and stimulate responsible and efficient reuse of precious biomedical data that cannot be reobtained.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 100

Dutch public summary

Longitudinale observationele en interventiestudies met uitgebreide data uit diverse bronnen zijn van onschatbare waarde voor biomedisch onderzoek. Datasets zoals vragenlijsten, fysieke en moleculaire metingen en scans zijn vaak gedurende een lange periode verzameld zonder rekening te houden met de FAIR-principes. Retrospectieve FAIRificatie is daarom essentieel voor toekomstig hergebruik. Hoewel FAIR-principes dit proces kunnen begeleiden, kan de praktische implementatie uitdagend zijn. In dit project ontwikkelen we stapsgewijze handleidingen, tools en toegangsprocedures om biomedische onderzoekers te helpen deze rijke datasets retrospectief te FAIRifiëren. Zo faciliteren en stimuleren we verantwoord en efficiënt hergebruik van waardevolle biomedische data die niet opnieuw kunnen worden verkregen.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 100

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Word count SEC31 (max. 150): 150

This project will increase the quality and reuse of existing invaluable health data. We will develop step-by-step tutorials on how to retrospectively FAIRify longitudinal biomedical data that has diverse data sources and needs consent for reuse, like observational cohort and intervention studies. Furthermore, workflows and tooling for implementing the steps in the FAIRification process will be developed. Finally, transparent data access procedures will be established. While focusing on the implementation at LUMC, generic modules will be made publicly available. The envisioned automated publication of the machine-readable metadata to the LUMC FAIR Data Point will enable automated harvesting by national metadata catalogues. Taking the data of the [Leiden Longevity Study](#)¹ and the [GOTO study](#)² as FAIRification use cases, this project paves the way for the many other LUMC studies to improve their [FAIR DataSet Maturity levels](#)³ (FAIR-DSM) and thereby contributes to a digital infrastructure supporting quality and reuse of health data.

3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

Word count SEC32 (max. 200): 178

Within LUMC there are many datasets present from relevant longitudinal observational and intervention studies with complex data assembly. However, there is little knowledge about the Open Science principles, and even less knowledge how to practically apply the Open Science principles on existing data sets. Which data-related platforms, applications, and procedures are recommended and which types of support are needed in the FAIRification process? Current guidelines describe WHAT needs to be done for FAIRification, but not HOW to do that in practice. Step-by-step tutorials will facilitate the adaptation towards reuse of ready available biomedical data. When more biomedical longitudinal and intervention study data would be at least findable and reusable for (LUMC) colleagues, potentially less studies have to be performed because existing data can be reused. Clear instructions and examples will enable researchers who collected biomedical longitudinal observational and intervention studies, implementation of such practices in their workflows. This project will describe and facilitate the practical steps that research teams need to take to improve study and datasets descriptions, leading to a higher [FAIR DataSet Maturity](#)³ (FAIR-DSM) level and findability.

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

Word count SEC33 (max. 200): 155

The proposed work in this project will result in clear step-by-step tutorials that (LUMC) biomedical researchers need to take for improving the [FAIR-DSM levels](#)³ of their existing longitudinal biomedical data from various sources. We will employ open standards such as the [Data Catalog Vocabulary \(DCAT\)](#)⁴ that is widely used in Europe. It is also the basis for [HealthDCAT-AP](#)⁵ which is developed to enable metadata exchange in the [European Health Data Space \(EHDS\)](#)⁶. We will make use of the FAIR Data Point technology that uses open and standardized protocols for metadata publishing. Tutorials and associated source code will be made publicly available under Creative Commons and Open Source licenses, respectively. The FAIRification tutorials, workflows, tooling and transparent processes will lead to many more shared biomedical scientific (LUMC) data sets in the future. By enhancing quality and richness of metadata, the project will facilitate findability in national metadata catalogues, accessibility through transparent data access procedures, and reusability.

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

Word count SEC41 (max. 750): 738

Over the past decades, numerous longitudinal observational and intervention studies have collected rich data from diverse sources—questionnaires, physical and molecular measures, and imaging. These datasets remain highly valuable for current biomedical research. However, many were created without applying FAIR principles, making retrospective FAIRification essential for reuse. While guidelines exist on what to do, researchers often lack clarity on how to implement them. To address this gap, we will develop practical, step-by-step tutorials, workflows and tooling to help biomedical researchers retrospectively FAIRify complex datasets to enable responsible and efficient data reuse.

In the past years we have put efforts to into the FAIRification of the [Leiden Longevity Study \(LLS\) data](https://github.com/LUMC-DCC/LLS-FAIRification/wiki)⁷ (<https://github.com/LUMC-DCC/LLS-FAIRification/wiki>)⁸. With the FAIRification of LLS data as a use case, we developed a vision on required step-by-step tutorials within the FAIRification process of longitudinal observational cohort data (Figure 1). Using LLS as primary use case, and a second study, the lifestyle intervention GOTO study, as use case for generalization of the developed tutorials, workflows and tooling, we will describe in detail the recommended practical steps in the FAIRification process of observational longitudinal and intervention studies with complex data assembly.

Figure 1. Envisioned FAIRification process of data from biomedical observational longitudinal and intervention studies with complex data assembly.

The [LLS](#)¹ and [GOTO](#)² study data offer valuable reuse potential due to their design, diverse and rich phenotypes, and multi-tissue molecular data. Researchers frequently inquire about accessing these datasets for replication or inclusion in larger initiatives such as meta-analyses. Also AI methodologists show interest due to the high-dimensional data ([Sluiskes et al., 2024](#))⁹. However, the lack of comprehensive codebooks, study descriptions, and formal access procedures leads to time-consuming responses to inquiries. There is a strong need to clearly retrospectively document study designs, measurement timepoints and methods, and data access procedures to support efficient reuse of LLS, GOTO, and other LUMC biomedical data with complex data assembly.

Presently in the LUMC, data capture using [CASTOR](#)¹⁰ is the only step in the data FAIRification process that has been described and communicated within LUMC. The FAIRification process that we currently envision continues with step 2. “Storage of captured data and metadata describing the data”, step 3. “Make the metadata machine readable”, and step 4. “Make the data accessible” (Figure 1).

This project is structured around 6 objectives:

1. Establish step-by-step tutorials for the retrospective FAIRification process of biomedical studies with complex data assembly in the LUMC
2. Provide tooling to facilitate (meta)data transfer from CASTOR into data warehouses or catalogues
3. Standardize metadata compliant with European standards (EHDS)⁶
4. Provide tooling to automate metadata extraction from local catalogue, and publication on the LUMC FAIR Data Point
5. Establish a general transparent data access procedure for LUMC biomedical studies
6. Establish the [FAIR-DSM level 2](#)³ (Described and contextualized data) for Leiden Longevity Study and GOTO study data

Approach

We will develop step-by-step tutorials, workflows, tooling and data access procedures that suit the LUMC infrastructure employing the LLS use case. By applying the concept tutorials, workflows and tooling to the GOTO study, we will generalize the tooling so that they serve different settings of biomedical studies with various data sources. In table 1, the deliverables of the current project are listed.

Table 1. Deliverables of the RetroFAIR project.

Workpackage	Code	Deliverable	Timing
WP1: FAIRification process	D1	Workflow describing the recommended steps of the LUMC retrospective FAIRification process and how to incorporate it in Data Management Plans.	Y1Q3
WP2. Store (Meta)Data	D2	Tooling to transfer data from CASTOR ¹⁰ into local data warehouse	Y1Q3
	D3	Tooling to transfer metadata from CASTOR ¹⁰ into local catalogue	Y1Q3
	D4	Tutorial for storage of different types of molecular data in data warehouse	Y1Q4
	D5	Tutorial for the storage of metadata on several levels (study, data set, collection of data sets, variable level)	Y1Q4
WP3. Make metadata machine readable	D6	Tooling to automatically extract and map metadata according to the Health-RI provided metadata schema from local catalogue and publish those on the LUMC Fair Data Point	Y2Q4
	D7	Protocol how to request persistent identifier for the local metadata catalogue accompanying and data warehouse	Y2Q2
WP4. Make Data Accessible	D8	Transparent procedure for LUMC data access requests, including forms and data licencing, data access rights	Y2Q3
	D9	Protocol how to link MICA ¹¹ to PODIUM data request portal ¹² (product of BBMRI-NL ¹³) and National Health Data Catalog ¹⁴ .	Y2Q4
	D10	LLS ¹ and GOTO ² study data at FAIR DSM level 2 ³ (Described and contextualized data)	Y2Q4

4.2 Team composition

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
<i>Dr. M. (Marian) Beekman</i>	<i>LUMC</i>	<i>LLS and GOTO study PI, writing meta data, study specific knowledge</i>	<i>Project manager WP2 leader WP4 leader</i>
<i>Dr. K.M. (Karin) van der Pal</i>	<i>LUMC</i>	<i>LUMC infrastructure, Head LUMC Data Competence Center,</i>	<i>WP1 leader</i>
<i>Dr. A (Anna) Niehues</i>	<i>LUMC</i>	<i>FAIR data and research software stewardship, coordination of FAIR implementation activities</i>	<i>WP3 leader</i>
	<i>LUMC</i>	<i>Study specific knowledge</i>	<i>Data steward with study specific knowledge</i>
	<i>LUMC</i>	<i>(Meta)Data storage and handling</i>	<i>Data manager</i>
	<i>LUMC</i>	<i>Interoperability, metadata standards, FDP, software development</i>	<i>FAIR data steward Data engineer</i>

To achieve the project’s goals, we bring together a diverse team with complementary expertise to enhance Open Science readiness for biomedical studies. Dr. Marian Beekman, assistant professor at Molecular Epidemiology (MOLEPI), brings deep study-specific knowledge of the Leiden Longevity Study¹ and GOTO² study, including data capture and biomaterial use. She contributed to the Dutch Data Prize 2018 winning BBMRI-Omics Consortium that made four levels of omics data in Dutch cohort data accessible for researchers, and currently contributes to the [Netherlands Cohorts Consortium \(NCC\)](#)¹⁵, focused on cohort data harmonization and sharing. Dr. Karin van der Pal, head of Advanced Data Management (ADM) and the LUMC Data Competence Center (DCC), leads initiatives on FAIR data, safe personal data handling, and Good Research Practice. She also coordinates the LUMC nodus of the national health research infrastructure [Health-RI](#)¹⁶, promoting data reuse and machine-actionable metadata. Dr. Anna Niehues, Coordinator Design & Analyse, offers expertise in FAIR data principles, metadata creation, and computational workflows. Supporting the team, technician XXXXX documents detailed metadata at variable level for LLS and GOTO, while YYYYY, data manager, oversees (meta)data storage using [OPAL data warehouse](#)¹⁷ and MICA catalogue¹¹. ZZZZZZ, FAIR data steward and engineer at ADM, specializes in automating metadata extraction and publication via the LUMC [FAIR Data Point](#).

This multidisciplinary team, with strong ties to national infrastructures [Health-RI](#)¹⁶ and [NCC](#)¹⁵, ensures comprehensive expertise in study specific knowledge, safe data processing, expertise on creating (machine readable) meta-data, informatics support, and FAIR implementation.

Word count SEC42 (max. 350): 343

4.3 Risk management

We consider our project a low risk project with high impact of the sharing of valuable longitudinal observational and intervention study datasets.

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
Changes in underlying tooling – like CASTOR ¹⁰ , OPAL ¹⁷ and MICA ¹¹	<i>Likelihood: medium Impact: medium</i>	<i>Communicate well with tool developers about (upcoming) changes, so we can anticipate on the changes in our tooling</i>
Changes/progression in (Health-RI) metadata schemas	<i>Likelihood: large Impact: medium</i>	<i>Keep in close contact with metadata standard developers. We will check on planned releases. Versioning of our tooling and indicating compliance with specific versions of released metadata standards.</i>

Word count SEC43 (max. 150): 97

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institution	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Project manager	HOT 2.1 - 14	LUMC	0.34	2	€ 50,216.30
Research analyst	HOT 2.1 - 11	LUMC	0.40	2	€ 40,108.00
Data manager	HOT 2.1 - 10	LUMC	0.90	2	€ 79,267.50
Specialist IT	HOT 2.1 - 11	LUMC	0.50	2	€ 50,135.00
General data steward (TBD)	HOT 2.1 - 11	LUMC	0.30	2	€ 30,081.00

Total Personnel requested: €249.807,80

Total Material/IT requested: €0,00

Total budget requested: €249.807,80

4.5 Budget justification

A project manager will be appointed. The general data steward (TBD) will describe the overall workflow of retrospective FAIRification process (D1). The data manager and the specialist IT will collaborate on the development and implementation of the tooling (D2, D3). The data manager will write step-by-step tutorials for the storage of metadata and the different molecular data (D4, D5). The data manager and the specialist IT will also jointly work on automated extraction of metadata and the mapping to the [standardized \(Health-RI\) metadata schema](#)¹⁸ (D6). The data manager will in addition write a protocol how to request persistent identifier for the local metadata catalogue (D7). The general data steward will develop a transparent data access procedure in accordance with EHDS, including forms, data licencing and data access rights (D8). The data manger will write a protocol how to link the local data catalogue with the data request portal of interest ([PODIUM](#)¹² or National Health Data Catalog¹⁴) (D9). PI of the LLS¹ and GOTO² study will jointly write the meta data with the [research analyst with study specific knowledge](#) (D10).

Word count SEC 45 (max. 200): 200

4.6 Impact plan

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 168

Table 2. Impact plan of the RetroFAIR project

Impact domain	Objective	Activities	Timeframe
Science	Disseminate the workflow for the retrospective FAIRification process	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Publication of retrospective FAIRification workflow on Zenya (LUMC repository) and on publicly available repository e.g. Open Science Framework 2.Communicate with other study PIs in LUMC and NCC¹⁵ about the retrospective workflow. 3.Presentations at meetings of national digital infrastructures like Health-RI¹⁶ and NCC¹⁵ 	M12-24
Science	Disseminate the tooling for the transfer of (meta)data to the local data warehouse and catalogue	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Publicly publish software on e.g. Github 2.Provide training to departmental data managers 3.Presentations at meetings of national digital infrastructures like Health-RI¹⁶ and NCC¹⁵ 	M18-24
Science	More open access biomedical scientific study data findable and reusable	1.Support LUMC longitudinal observational and intervention studies (f.e. NEO, PROSPER, MEGA, TRUST, APOP) in the retrospective FAIRification process by LUMC DCC	M24+
Society	Better answers to relevant questions about health due to more high quality available datasets	1.Promotion of retrospective FAIRification of longitudinal observational and intervention studies with complex data assembly.	M24+

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

Word count SEC51 (max 300): 138

All deliverables D1-10 of this project (Table 1) need to be sustained and maintained in the long-term. The LUMC prioritizes data stewardship to facilitate the transparency of research and reuse of data. The LUMC ADM section, which is the LUMC facility for advanced data management (ADM), has experts available on FAIR data stewardship and implements a GRP quality system for securing quality and improving research efficiency. The delivered workflows (D1, D4, D5, D7, D8) will be sustained and supported by the LUMC ADM/DCC with FAIR data stewards. The delivered tools (D2, D3, D6) will be maintained by data engineers of ADM/DCC. The sustainability of the available LLS and GOTO study data will be covered for the next 10 year (data manager) if the NWO Roadmap LSRI application of the NCC will be granted (decision expected in October 2025).

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

During this project, we will develop tools, including scripts and workflows supporting automated mapping and publishing metadata of longitudinal observational and intervention studies.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

The source will be managed using a platform supporting Git-based version control (GitHub). Changes to source will be documented using [Conventional Commits](#)¹⁹. We will use [Semantic Versioning](#)²⁰ (MAJOR.MINOR.PATCH) for releasing versions of the software. Major releases will be archived ([Zenodo](#)²¹, [Software Heritage](#)²²).

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?

The software will be made publicly available in a repository on [GitHub](#)²³

. It will be released under a suitable Open Source license, preferably Apache 2.0 or MIT. A LICENSE file will be added to the repository.

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

A CITATION.cff file will be added to the repository.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

Software documentation will include user documentation as part of the step-by-step tutorials developed in this project. They will include installation, configuration and usage instructions for each of the practical steps. A deployment documentation will outline system requirements, dependencies, and setup instructions for supported environments. A developer documentation will include an overview of the code structure and content. Additionally, the source code will include in-line comments and docstrings.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

The developed software will serve as a showcase for metadata transfer between different applications. We are open to collaborate with other researchers or organizations to achieve the desired functionality. To support collaboration, we will add contribution guidelines to the repository. The tooling will be governed by the LUMC DCC.

7. How will your software be tested?

We will write and run unit tests for core functions.

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

We will assess all dependencies for license compatibility.

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

Source will be packaged as part of tutorials. Input/output examples representing our use cases will be included for reproducibility and included in the documentation.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

We will support questions through GitHub issues. We will organize sessions to showcase and demonstrate the tooling, providing hands-on support.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

Our software will serve as an implementation example. Long term maintenance of our tooling is not planned.

However, we will reach out to providers of the systems we aim to integrate, to explore taking up the newly developed functionality into their applications.

Section 6: References

1. <https://leidenlanglevan.nl/>
2. <https://leidenlanglevan.nl/samen-uit-samen-thuis-studie/>
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5. <https://github.com/healthDCAT-AP>
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18. <https://github.com/Health-RI/health-ri-metadata/>
19. <https://www.conventionalcommits.org/en/v1.0.0/#summary>
20. <https://semver.org/>
21. <https://zenodo.org/>
22. <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>
23. <https://github.com/LUMC-DCC>

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.